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**FORCED LAND REMOVALS:
The Unjust History of Tshikota¹and its People**

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Abstract

Forced land removals in South Africa began long before the introduction of the homeland system. Mass colonial appropriations of land preceded the legislative land-disposition processes of apartheid. People were forcefully removed from one place to another for "reasons" such as farming, mining or urban expansion. In other cases, violence was not used but through empty promises. The preceding mainly benefited the white minority. Over time, the Land Act of 1913 was an important legislative tool to facilitate forced rural removals, which earmarked less than 13% of the land for black occupation (Feinberg & Horn, 2009). Consequently, the apartheid government established reservations for Bantustans. Individual black land ownership was a thing of the future. This article is about the unjust story of Tshikota and its people. It adopts a historical studies approach and incorporates a narrative analysis. The article discusses how one of the original residents of Makhado dispersed in what was then Dzata. This article attempts to chronologically reconstruct the events that have led to the Tshikota known today.

Keywords: Tshikota, Forced land removals, Apartheid, Land-dispossession

¹Established in the early 1940s, Tshikota is a black township approximately 3km west of Louis Trichard in the Vhember District, Limpopo Province.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Forced removals³ in South Africa started long before the homeland system was implemented during the pre-apartheid era. People were forcefully removed from one place to another for segregative reasons. Pre-apartheid mainly included white settlers not wanting to integrate with natives – and during the apartheid era, the government intended to use the land for specific purposes such as mining, farming, or extending existing white settler towns. Forced removals went hand in hand with incorporation. In other words, they did not necessarily mean that once natives were forcefully removed from their land, they would automatically be incorporated into bantustans or homeland. The preceding meant that one would exist without citizenship or a pass, making life harder to move around different towns, let alone elders who need to obtain their pension grant. Various factors were considered before people or land was incorporated, such as the number of people in the township or affected rural areas⁴.

As learnt in this article, the apartheid government established reserves, subsequently turned into bantustans. Many natives were forcefully removed from their original land to these areas, also known as scheduled native areas, squatters or black spots. Black land ownership could only be established by allocation – individual ownership was unknown, and land could only be allocated to legal community members or group members. As the right was invested in a group and not individuals, only the group had the exclusive and full and unhampered enjoyment, use and profit of land.

Section 1 of The Native's Land Act prohibited natives from entering into an agreement concerning purchasing, hiring or acquiring land from a white person, especially land outside Scheduled Native Areas. However, in some cases, the

³The concept of forced removal had a broad connotation. It covered situations where people were forcefully and violently removed from their land. The government used technical methods to lure people to leave their land voluntarily - for instance, promising them new houses and better living conditions.

⁴ Regarding the Borders of Particular States Extension Amendment Act, the South African government could transfer land and people to the jurisdiction of the Independent homelands of Transkei, Bophuthatswana, Ciskei and Venda.

Governor-General had powers to approve the latter land transaction (Jones, 1965; Omer-Cooper, 1967; Letsoalo, 1987). Furthermore, Section 2 provided for the appointment of a commission to report on the land that should be separated for exclusive native and non-native occupation (SA, 1913).

Naturally, people were not pleased with this idea of forced removal. In most cases, natives were forcefully removed from fertile land to rocky areas where they could not plough or graze their livestock. The forced land removals continued for many years and culminated in the 1970s and 1980s. Initially, there was little that natives could do to halt operations of forced land removals – however, as these were sometimes done repeatedly to the same community (the gist of this article), they gradually started to resist. Fortunately, in 1985, the policy of forced removal was stopped and replaced by incorporation. The article discusses how one of the original inhabitants of Makhado was relocated repeatedly around the Soutpansberg region in the northern Transvaal⁵ - first (i) from Getrudesburg to Masagani, (ii) from Masagani to Tshikota and then (iii) from Tshikota to Vleifontien.

1.2. Drivers of land dispossessions and forced land removals

The South African Constitution of 1910 and other legal institutions promoted racial segregation and inequality systems. Consequently, 7.3% of the land in South Africa was set aside for indigenous settlement (Maylam, 1986; Feinberg & Horn, 2009). In addition, Land Acts such as The Natives Land Act No. 27 of 1913 and The Natives Administration Act No. 38 of 1927⁶ reinforced the promotion of land accumulation for white settlers through disposing of land from natives (De Beer, 2001).

⁵ The Northern Transvaal was later named the Northern Province and later known as the Limpopo Province.

⁶ The Native's Administration Act of 1927 under General Hertzog's government maintained the land inequality brought forth by the promulgation of the 1913 Native Land Act. Hertzog's government aimed at reducing the 7.3% of land initially allocated for black occupation. By promoting the reduction of land for Africans, Hertzog pleased white farmers and gained loyal white supporters in return (Platzky & Walker, 1985). Furthermore, the Act clarified the promotion of racial and spatial segregation by limiting integration between natives and white farmers. As such, the Governor-General under Hertzog's government had specific powers to rule by proclamation in all native areas.

As a successor to the two Land Acts, namely, 1913 and 1936, was the Group Areas Act 1950, later consolidated by Group Areas Act No. 36 1966. This law significantly impacted racial segregation in South Africa (Horrell, 1982). Consequently, the law authorised the President of the State to delimit certain areas of land exclusively for the possession and occupation of certain racial groups, namely Native Africans, whites and coloureds. Persons not belonging to the same racial group as the group area were therefore considered disqualified and could not occupy land in a group area unless they had a permit (Group Areas Act 1950).

1.3. Methodology

This study is based on a traditional storytelling research approach and a historical literature review of secondary data. This approach collects stories from participants about their life experiences and what they mean to them. It then analyses these stories to understand their impact and what we can learn from them (Datta, 2018). Traditional Western research methods to explore indigenous perspectives have often been found inadequate and ineffective by indigenous people in gathering information and encouraging discussion. On the contrary, traditional storytelling as a research method connects indigenous worldviews and shapes the research approach, the theoretical and conceptual frameworks, and epistemology, methodology and ethics.

This study's approach was as follows: the participants were elders in my family and the elders in the community. These individuals are respected for their knowledge, wisdom and experience, and their stories provide insight into family and community history and traditions. In collecting these stories, I have engaged with them through regular visits and conversations, attending traditional ceremonies and gatherings, and participating in community activities such as muthangano (gathering). Our elders have a habit of sharing their stories. This is the general relationship and interaction between the elders and the youth. Therefore, elders share their stories orally. Only recently, after years of continually repeating these stories, have I

decided to record and analyse them to understand their implications and what we need to note as the youth of Makhado as we move through our spaces like Tshikota, Vlifontein and Waterval. As I analysed these stories, I identified a common theme and pattern of forced land evictions. I realised that these stories are not just historical artefacts but living expressions of contemporary socio-economic and spatial reality. As such, I consider how the stories are still relevant and meaningful today, particularly to inform and inspire current and future generations of Makhado.

That being said, the interpretative phenomenological analysis was adopted as it captures a specific phenomenon, in this case, the living experience of the socio-economic and spatial reality of the natives of the Soutpansberg region. Adopting a research paradigm is essential when interpreting living reality. Kuhn (1970) defines the research paradigm as a general understanding of how problems are perceived and addressed. The preceding is approached from an ontological and epistemological viewpoint (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). This work's interpretive research paradigm allows for subjectivity and responding flexibly to changes in reality.

2. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF THE SOUTPANSBERG REGION

The human settlement history of each region can go back hundreds and even thousands of years. This article takes the 1500s as a starting point. According to Wilson, quoted in Thompson (1994), the Arab pilot of Vasco da Gama⁷ indicated in 1530 a place rich in gold – the territory of the VhaVenda people. The VhaVenda are known to have been responsible for Mesina's gold and copper trade and the upper layers of archaeological remains at Mapungubwe and Bambandyallo between the 11th and 15th centuries (Ivarsson, 2007).

Around 1688, a ruler named Dimbanyika managed to consolidate smaller communities in the region into the so-called Venda (Nemudzivhadi, 1998). Venda

⁷ Ahmad Ibn Majid.

also consisted of several smaller, well-established communities settled in the Soutpansberg region, including the Vha-Vhirwa who lived west of the salt pan, the Vha-Ngona in the central parts of the mountain, the Vha-Lembethu in the north-eastern region, and the Vha-Mbedzi of the central-eastern parts as well as the Vha-Tavatsindi and the Vha-Dau. This region was known as Dzata.

In the 1800s, the Nyelele, also known as Nzhelele, and Tshirululuni shared the capital of the Venda Kingdom. This area, known as Songozwi, was used for habitation, and the grazing land lay below the mountain where Louis Trichardt stands today. The VhaVenda king VhoRamabulana and his people could see when their enemies were approaching. In addition, the region was free of malaria and the tsetse fly. When the first Voortrekkers Langhans van Rensburg and Louis Trichardt arrived in the Soutpansberg region, King VhoRamabulana was at the head of the Venda state.

The settlement of Europeans in the Soutpansberg region began in the 19th century. The whites had begun to settle lands occupied by the VhaVenda people. Life among the VhaVenda people implied that the new white settlers began to undermine the authority of the traditional rulers and even take away the land (Tempelhoff & Nemudzivhadi, 1997). Ultimately, in the mid and late 19th century, under King VhoMakhado, the VhaVenda no longer welcomed the presence of the white settlers in the Soutpansberg region. King Makhado was so opposed to the apartheid government during his reign in the 1890s, they even had to shelve plans to found a town in the Soutpanburg Mountains. Only after the death of King VhoMakhado in 1895 were the white settlers able to infiltrate Soutpansberg (ibid.). For the VhaVenda people, the death of Chief Vho Makhado was a setback as the white settlers conquered the community. In essence, the death of King VhoMakhado paved the way for the founding of Louis Trichardt in the late 19th century; on February 22 1899,⁸ to be specific.

⁸ The proclamation was published in the Staatscourant der Zuid-Afrikaansche Republiek on February 22, 1899.37.

The primary purpose of the preceding historical background is to establish that the Soutpansberg region comprised complex, organised, and thriving human settlements before the arrival of white settlers. The VhaVenda people had occupied the Dzata (Soutpansberg region) for centuries and even traded gold and copper with Arab and other merchants Thompson (1994). These were the same people who occupied Mapungubwe. From a pre-colonial and apartheid perspective, white settlers disrupted the region's indigenous civilisation. With this historical background, this article focuses on the colonial and apartheid-centric disturbances that the native peoples of the Soutpansberg region endured in the form of land confiscations and continuous forced land evictions.

3. GETRUBESBURG: THE COMMENCEMENT OF FORCED LAND REMOVALS

Located 4 kilometres south of Louis Trichardt, Gertrudesburg's history dates back to the late 18th century. It was a settlement dominated by the VhaVenda people. However, there were other ethnic groups, such as BaPedi and Shangaan. These communities owned cattle, sheep, goats, and chickens. In 1899, the Berlin Mission von Gertrudsberg led the establishment of the area when Pastor E. Gottschling founded the Gertrudsberg Mission Station on the Ledig farm. Founded mainly for the natives in the late 19th century, the mission station became an important centre for the native communities in the Soutpansberg region. It was a place of religion, education and, more importantly, home to many of the people who worked as gardeners and domestic workers in Louis Trichardt.

White settlers increased over time, and more land was required. With the implementation of the Native Land Act of 1913, many natives who lived as landowners and sharecroppers near Louis Trichardt lost their homes as their lands were expropriated to form part of the town of Louis Trichardt. People whose lands had been confiscated were relocated to neighbouring black reservations (The SPP Report 1983). In the early 1960s, residents of Gertrudesburg were told they needed

to move. Consequently, the residents of Gertrudesburg were forcefully evicted from their homes to Masagani⁹, a hill northwest of Louis Trichardt intended to be developed as a black township. The Masagani site was founded in 1918.

Until 1954, people lived on top of the hill just northwest of the town centre. The reasons for moving the original township are unclear. Possibly, the white residents had too clear a view of it. The new township was built on a valley out of sight of the white residents. It was not built to improve the residents' living standards; as the roads were terrible, there was no electricity or even water-borne sewerage, just a bucket system (TRAC 1988, p. 1).

Others who owned livestock were taken to nearby villages or reserved areas about 15 kilometres southwest of Louis Trichardt, where they were allocated plots of land to build their homesteads¹⁰. These villages were and still are known as Ha-Sinthumule and fell under the Venda Republic. Those who resettled to Masagani were also assigned sites where they could build homesteads but were not allowed to keep livestock. In Masagani, however, each head of the family had to pay 25 cents. Most of these homesteads were traditional African huts insulated with bags or sacks, and during cold winters, some residents used these sacks as blankets. The preceding resulted in the area being named Masagani.

During this time, the areas adjacent to the city were affected by several forced displacements typical of other parts of South Africa. Namely; removal of black spots; removal of farms; moves due to housing consolidation, moves from urban and informal areas; and infrastructural and military resettlement and implementation of the Group Areas Act 1950 (Meth, 1999).

⁹ Masagani is a TshiVenda word directly translating to bags or sacks in English.

¹⁰ Some 200 people in 1963 were moved with the help of the military to the western parts of the area of Chief Vho Kutama.

3.2. Forced removals from Masagani to Tshikota

Although the apartheid government forcefully moved the people of Gertrudesburg to Masagani, it never intended for them to live there permanently. The tightening of apartheid legislation and the implementation of the Natives (Urban Areas) Consolidation Act of 1945 were intended to relocate people who had settled in Masagani¹¹. Louis Trichardt's local authority began clearing a piece of land about 3 kilometres southwest of Masagani; this area would become known as Tshikota¹².

Tshikota embodied the qualities of a classic black apartheid township, similar to other black townships in apartheid South Africa, such as Soweto, Soshaguve, Khayalitsh, Mhluzi and many others. By the mid-1950s, preparations for Tshikota were complete, and again, as before and before then, residents of Maganagi were forcefully taken from their homes to Tshikota. In 1957, there was no one left in Masagani. At least this time, they were allocated houses for the 99-year lease. Therefore, they were automatically vested with Section 10(1)(a) and (b) of the Blacks (Urban Areas) Consolidation Act.

At first glance, one would assume that the development of Tshikota was intended to improve the living conditions of the people of Masagani. However, this was not the case. The aim was to force Masagani residents to move to Tshikota as Louis Trichardt's town grew westward. Additionally, and in keeping with apartheid planning principles, the hill would act as a buffer between black and white

¹¹ The Group Areas Act of 1950 made it difficult for blacks who claimed they were entitled to remain in a white urban area due to their birthright. There was no accommodation for blacks in the inner areas of towns and cities. Furthermore, The Promotion of Black Self-Government Act of 1959, through which homelands were created, provided an outlet for the apartheid government to further push blacks out of white urban areas.

¹² By Government Notice 2011 of September 24 1948, and acting in terms of Section 2 (1) (a) of the Black (Urban Areas) Consolidation Act 25 of 1945, the then Minister of Native Affairs approved the defining, setting apart and laying out by the Municipality of Louis Trichardt of a particular piece of land as a location for the occupation, residence and other requirements of blacks. The area fell under the jurisdiction of the Louis Trichardt Municipality and was known as Tshikota. It was clear at this early stage that Tshikota was intended as the urban township for black residents in Louis Trichardt. Residents were required to obtain permission in Section 10 of the Black (Urban Areas) Consolidation Act to reside there.

settlements – a classic apartheid planning style. The houses in Tshikota were built on flat foundations with inferior bricks; The church was not adequately surveyed, planned and built. In addition, when the residents of Masagani were resettled in Tshikota, there were no educational, religious or health institutions.

Nevertheless, a primary school called Masedi and a Dutch Reformed Church were established over time. Later, a clinic and men's hostel were added. By 1980, Tshikota had a thriving and harmonious population of nearly 10,000 (Sadiki, 2000). It consisted mainly of the VhaVenda, Shangaan and BaPedi people.

Though initially disliking the township, residents of Tshikota have come to call it home after more than a decade there, and for the first time almost five generations later, they have not feared forced displacement. Unfortunately, this was short-lived. This was recognised when some Tshikota residents began approaching Louis Trichardt's local authority to build their own houses or expand the existing ones, but this was refused. This was further realised when no more houses were built by the local authority, and the waiting list grew longer and longer, only the reoccupation of abandoned houses as some residents were relocated to nearby rural villages to escape the shekels of apartheid¹³ - urban black-segregated Tshikota township.

Subsequently, the apartheid government decided to expel the residents of Tshikota from other areas under the control of their homelands. In doing so, the apartheid government probably wanted to rid itself of its responsibility towards many black South Africans. Residents were not consulted as they would not support the eviction.

¹³ Note that during this period, legislation relating to influx control was still applicable, meaning only persons qualified in terms of Section 10(1)(a) or (b) of the Black (Urban Areas) Consolidation Act 25 of 1945 applied. By the 1980s, Tshikota had a population of approximately 10,000, consisting mainly of three ethnic groups: VhaVenda, Shangaan and BaPedi.

4. FORCED REMOVALS¹⁴ OF TSHIKOTA'S RESIDENTS

When Venda became independent in 1979, there was pressure from the apartheid government for the VhaVenda people to leave Tshikota for the Venda Republic. This came after Venda's then-president, Chief Patric Mphhephu, urged the South African government to incorporate the town of Louis Trichardt and all neighbouring farms into Venda. When that request was denied, the apartheid government was more determined than ever to forcefully remove all black residents of Louis Trichardt, specifically Tshikota. The apartheid government aimed to forcefully transfer the VhaVenda to Venda, the Shangaan to Gazankulu, and the BaPedi to Lebowa¹⁵ - then known as homelands or nation-states.

The same tactic¹⁶ was then used to relocate the residents of Masagani by preparing an area with the promise of greener pastures, only this time, the tactic for forcefully relocating Tshikota residents to Vleifontein was used. The apartheid government developed Vleifontein to house the VhaVenda people of Tshikota. At the time, however, Vleifontein was a trust land near Venda but within the borders of South Africa. Tshikota was declared a hostel for black men on December 31, 1981, by Deputy Society Minister G Morrison to expedite eviction. According to the original statement, the local authority refused to recognise the residents or consider Tshikota a township. As a result, no steps were taken to preserve the community.

In line with apartheid policy, the population of Tshikota was ethnically divided and removed to areas designated to be the homelands of the residents. Thus, between 1982 and 1985, most of the VhaVenda residents of Tshikota were moved

¹⁴ In 1982/83, Venda-speaking people were moved to Vleifontein, a trust farm on the border of South Africa and Venda. Moreover, in 1985, the Shangaan-speaking were removed and taken to Waterval near Elim Hospital. On April 1 1986, Vleifontein was incorporated into Venda.

¹⁵ The BaPedi-speaking people were scheduled to move to Seshego in Lebowa, near Pietersburg (known today as Polokwane). However, this did not occur due to resistance by the residents, who were more determined to remain in Tshikota than ever before. They even established a committee to represent the remaining residents in Tshikota. Its main object was to oppose and fight all government action, which would lead to the removal of the families who had remained at Tshikota.

¹⁶ Those who wanted to leave were promised government-built houses in Vleifontein at a compelling R1500,00 for two rooms and a toilet.

to a new town called Vleifontein, situated 25 kilometres from Louis Trichardt on the border of the homeland of Venda (TRAC 1988, p. 1).

In 1982, after Government Notice 2840, the residents of Tshikota were informed that the community would soon be demolished and that they should move voluntarily. In 1982 and 1983, a large part, an estimated 7,000 inhabitants of the municipality, were relocated to Vleifontein and Waterval (Annon, 1992). In January 1986, Mr Ockers, an official with the Northern Transvaal Development Board, told the remaining residents, most of them BaPedi, to prepare to leave as the move would take place on March 15 1986. He instructed them to go to Seshego so the township could become a residential area for single male workers. In 1987, the matter regarding Tshikota was debated in Parliament. Mr C. Heunis explained that the residents of Tshikota had to leave the country and go to nearby nation-states. The ministers reasoned that the existing black towns were tiny and economically unviable.

From the 1980s, the pressure on the people of Tshikota to move became much more significant. The first indication that something very ominous was brewing was when the Northern Transvaal Development Board conducted a comprehensive survey of the township's residents in 1980. Some residents allege that an essential function of the survey was to establish which residents had formal education. Those households with some formal education were initially left alone. The Board first approached illiterate or semi-literate household heads. It is alleged that Board officials told these residents that they had to move and that if they did not move voluntarily, they would not obtain a house and would have to build their homes themselves (TRAC,1988:1).

At first, residents of Tshikota refused to move. However, Northern Transvaal Administration Board officials went door to door, demanding residents sign documents entitling them to receive government-built homes if they agreed to move. They were reminded that if they refused to leave voluntarily, their homes would be

bulldozed, and they would forego a new home in Vleifontein¹⁷. As can be seen from reading TRAC (1988) above, committee officials even went so far as to target the illiterate of Tshikota first, another tactic used by the apartheid government to speed up the process. In the end, many residents signed¹⁸ the documents, unaware of the impact, a throwback to their fear of eviction. Ultimately, those who succumbed to the pressure, those who were coerced, and those who were tricked were taken to their respective homelands with their belongings. By 1988, there were only about 40 households left in Tshikota. To perpetuate the apartheid system, a cohesive community living in a township was torn apart, homes destroyed, and residents relocated far from their jobs.

4.2. Problems encountered by the residents in Vleifontein

After moving from Tshikota to Vleifontien, the residents immediately faced several challenges, the biggest of which was the commute from Vleifonteun to Louis Trichardt. Note that Vleifontein is approximately 25 kilometres from Louis Trichardt. That was more than eight times the distance travelled by residents from Tshikota to Louis Trichardt. Almost all Vleifontein residents were employed in Louis Trichardt as they needed reliable transport. There was only one bus available, which was insufficient because it could not meet demand independently. The bus could carry people only thrice daily: morning, afternoon and evening. If a person missed a bus in the morning, they would have to wait for the afternoon. Perhaps even more detrimental than access to adequate transportation was the resulting cost.

From the long but reasonable walking distance to Louis Trichardt to paying around R11.00c for a monthly pass was an added financial drain. The workers earned, on

¹⁷ The Louis Trichardt local authority was also a stumbling block. It no longer wanted the existence of the township. It continued to threaten the remaining residents with removal. The people were confused and did not know how long they would remain at Tshikota. As a result, some people started to leave one by one. As they left, the local authority demolished their houses.

¹⁸ Many residents signed the documents, and the Venda people were eventually removed and taken to Vleifontein. Shangaan people were moved to Waterval. Once they had moved, their homes, churches and clinics were demolished, leaving the remaining houses standing amongst the ruins.

average, less than R 100 a month. Other problems included inappropriate accommodation, bad hygiene, water pollution, no access to public phones, post offices, and decent grocery stores (Sadiki, 2000). The move's effects were even more pronounced when young men who previously had Section 10 rights were forced to work on a contract basis. The move from Tshikota to Vleifontein was a process during which the people were gradually stripped of their South African citizenship¹⁹. Only after the forced resettlement did they realise they would be incorporated into self-governing or independent homelands and lose their rights as South African citizens. In a letter to the minister dated February 25, 1986, an ad hoc committee based in Vietfontein wrote:

We only moved from Tshikota because we were told the location would be broken down. People did not want to move but were forced to sign their agreement one by one and at night, which we did under duress... When we moved to Vleifontein, we were told to apply for citizenship. We were amazed to hear this. We were not told of this before we left the location. We feel that we were tricked. Pensioners cannot get their pensions without a Venda identity document, our young men now have to work on contract, and all residents in government service have to have Venda ID to keep their jobs (TRAC 1988, p. 2).

On March 27, 1986, Vleifontein was incorporated into Venda. The residents' first indication of their new status came via a news broadcast on Radio Venda; they were not officially informed. In addition, the law did not provide for a hearing of those affected. The President only had to declare that a particular area did not belong to South Africa. This meant that the previous residents of Tshikota had to acquire citizenship of the Republic of Venda before receiving pensions or retaining public

¹⁹ On Friday, June 13 1986, a bus full of workers travelling from Vleifontein to Louis Trichardt was Stopped at a roadblock by Venda Police and Army members near Elim Hospital. There were close to 100 passengers on the bus at the time. The driver was forced to drive the bus to Tshitale Police Station, where all the passengers were assaulted by police using sjamboks, rifle butts, and open hands. They were assaulted indiscriminately without regard to sex or age. Later that day, the bus was released (Bester, 1992).

service employment. Overall, they were subject to a different executive and judicial system.

5. CONCLUSION

Forced resettlements adversely altered the lives of the indigenous people of the Soutpasburg region and South Africa. This resulted in constant fear of where you will live tomorrow or what will happen next. Many have been separated from their families and friends. No one should ever be forced to move from their country to where they call home. This article illustrates the cruel quality of the apartheid system and how people's lives have been disrupted to further its ends. The apartheid government legislated to expel the VhaVenda, Shangaan and BaPedi-speaking people from Tshikota. These people were stripped of all their rights and privileges in South Africa.

In conclusion, forced land removals in South Africa have a long and complex history that predates the introduction of the apartheid homeland system. The forced removals were motivated by various reasons, such as farming, mining, urban expansion, and the segregation of white settlers from native populations. The Land Act of 1913 was a key legislative tool used by the apartheid government to facilitate forced rural removals and establish reservations or bantustans for black communities. As discussed in this article, the story of Tshikota and its people is just one example of the unjust treatment of black South Africans and the impact of forced removals on their lives. It is crucial to acknowledge and understand this history to ensure that such injustices are not repeated in the future.

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